

Documentation on Changes made to CONP Publication and Commercialization Policies

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Introduction

This document outlines the major revisions made to the CONP Publication Policy and CONP Commercialization Policy since the draft versions of those documents were uploaded to conp.ca on July 19, 2019. These revisions were made based on the input of the CONP Ethics and Governance Committee given before and during the September 20th, 2019 committee meeting.

The new versions of the policies will be uploaded to conp.ca and the older draft versions are archived in the CONP Zenodo.

Changes and Revisions

1. Change in Approach to Best Practices

The most important change made to the policies are that they have been revised to reflect a best practices approach. Whereas the draft versions of the policies concentrated on setting the conditions for accessing, using, and uploading material on the CONP Portal, the new versions, approved by the CONP Ethics and Governance Committee on September 20th 2019, recommend best practices and consequently have a much broader scope. The recommended best practices the policies contain are now more broadly applicable and are directed to the CONP, neuroscience resource sharing platforms, and the Canadian Neuroscience community as a whole.

This change in approach to best practices is reflected in every section of the policies. A typical example is subsection 3.3 of the Commercialization Policy, where the language has been changed from “The CONP strongly encourages users...” to “The CONP should strongly encourage members of the Canadian neuroscience community...”. Furthermore, a paragraph has been added to subsection 3.3 addressed specifically to “Neuroscience resource sharing platforms”. This additional paragraph is also typical of the changes made to other sections.

Another typical example of the broader scope of the revised policies can be found in subsections 5.3 and 6.3 of the Publication Policy. Whereas the draft versions of the policies discussed only the sharing of derived data and modified software, the new versions discuss the sharing of all research data and software. These scope broadening changes are also reflected throughout each section of both policies.

Despite the changes discussed above the substantive nature of the policy approaches has not changed significantly. They still aim to encourage maximally open sharing of research resources and preventing the use of shared resources from being restricted.

2. Change in the Title of the Policies

The title of both policies has been changed to reflect the new best practices approach. The result is that the titles found in both draft versions are now followed by “: Best Practices in Open Neuroscience”.

3. Policies Combined into Single Booklet for Open Science in Action Symposium

The version of the policies uploaded to Zenodo is a single booklet containing both policies. The booklet was compiled by Mr. Matthieu Dupuis for the Open Science in Action Symposium at The Neuro held on November 18, 2019.

4. Page 2 Removal

The second page of both policies has been removed to match the format of the CONP Ethics and Data Governance Framework.

5. Stronger Language Related to No Restrictive Patenting

The language in subsection 2.3 of the Commercialization Policy has been altered to reflect a stronger stance against attempts to obtain patent rights that could interfere with shared resources. This change is based on feedback received from Mr. Walter Stewart on the CONP Ethics and Governance Committee.

6. Change in “open license” Language

Wherever possible references to “open licenses” have been made more specific. For example, instead of referring to using “open licenses” or “an open license” then language has been changed to “open data licenses” or “open software licenses”. This revision is based on the feedback of Mr. Adrian Thorogood, Ethics Manager for the CONP Ethics and Governance Committee.

7. Short Paragraphs Concerning Coming to Agreement on Open Science Goals

Language has been added to sections 2, 3, 5, and 6 of the Publication Policy recommending that “co-authors, and those substantially involved in generating a publication, should come to agreement about relevant open science goals as early as possible in the research lifecycle”. This revision is based on feedback received from Dr. Naser Muja, Executive Director of the CONP.

8. Updated Versions of the Policies

Since the policies will have to be updated from time to time to reflect evolving best practices subsection 1.3 has been added to the Publication Policy and subsection 1.4 to the Commercialization Policy explaining that updated versions will be posted to the CONP website and old versions will be found on the CONP Zenodo. Creating an amending procedure was suggested by Mr. Roland Nandler of the CONP Ethics and Governance Committee.

9. Public Domain Dedication for Software

Sections 4 and 6 of the Commercialization Policy have been revised to include the possibility of dedicating software to the public domain through a public domain dedication.

10. Rights Waiver Language Changed to Public Domain Dedication

Throughout both policies the term “rights waiver” has been replaced with the more commonly used term “public domain dedication”.

11. References to the Portal Terms of Use and CONP Contributor Agreement Removed

References to the Portal Terms of Use and CONP Contributor Agreement have been removed to reflect the change in approach to a broad best practices policy.

12. References to Additional Information Pages Removed

References to Additional Information Pages have been removed and replaced with recommendations that the CONP collect and create information and guidance tools.

13. Addition of Language Around Avoiding Journals Requiring Assignment of Data Copyright

A sentence was added to subsection 5.2 of the Publication Policy saying that journals that require an author to assign copyright in data to the journal or publisher should be avoided. This revision was made at the suggestion of Mr. Walter Stewart of the CONP Ethics and Governance Committee.